

18. Uluslararası Güncel Araştırmalarla Sosyal Bilimler Kongresi Tam Metinleri
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ÖN SÖZ

18. Uluslararası Güncel Araştırmalarla Sosyal Bilimler Kongresi, 08-11 Ekim 2024 tarihlerinde Ankara'da gerçekleşecektir. Bu kongre, Saybilder Topluluğunun organizasyonunda ve başta Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli Üniversitesi, Mardin Artuklu Üniversitesi, Carthage University olmak üzere çeşitli yükseköğretim kurumlarının ilmi desteği ile düzenlenmektedir. Kongreye 6 farklı ülkeden davetli konuşmacı davet edilmiştir. Aynı zamanda Türkçe, İngilizce ve Arapça duyurular yapılarak bilim insanlarına çağrıda bulunulmuştur. Bu çağrılar sonrasında Türkiye hariç 12 farklı ülkeden (Birleşik Arap Emirlikleri, Cezayir, Fas, Irak, Katar, Kazakistan, Libya, Mısır, Suudi Arabistan Krallığı, Tunus, Umman, Ürdün) sözlü bildiri kongre programına dâhil edilmiştir. Tüm bildiriler kör hakemlik sürecinden geçirildikten sonra sunuma kabul veya reddi gerçekleştirilmiştir. Bu süreç içerisinde bildirilerin önemli bir kısmına hakemlerden düzeltme talebi gelmiştir. Hakemler tarafından talep edilen düzeltmelerin yapılıp yapılmadığı da özenle kontrol edilmiş ve düzeltilerden sonra kabul mektupları düzenlenerek yazarlarına gönderilmiştir.

Başvuru süreci sonucunda 73'ü Türk bilim insanları tarafından ve 77'si farklı ülkelerden katılan bilim insanları tarafından hazırlanmış toplam 150 bildiri sözlü sunuma uygun bulunmuştur. Bu kitapta kongrede sunulan bildirilere ait tam metinler yer almaktadır.

Kongrenin bilim insanları arasındaki iletişimi kuvvetlendirmesini, bilgi alışverişini arttırmasını, ortak çalışma zeminlerini oluşturmasını, milletimize, insanlığa ve bilgiyle amel edenlere faydalı olmasını diliyorum.

Prof. Dr. Hüseyin Akyüz
Düzenleme Kurulu Başkanı

مقدمة

يسرنا أن نقدم لكم هذا الكتاب الذي يضم مجموعة الأبحاث الكاملة التي قُدمت خلال فعاليات المؤتمر الدولي الثامن عشر للدراسات الاجتماعية والتاريخية والقانونية، الذي عُقد في العاصمة التركية أنقرة خلال الفترة من 8 إلى 11 أكتوبر. كان هذا المؤتمر فرصة مميزة لتبادل الأفكار والمعرفة بين نخبة من الباحثين والأكاديميين المتخصصين في مجالات الدراسات الاجتماعية والتاريخية والقانونية، حيث تميز بالتنوع الفكري والتخصصي الذي يعكس تطور هذه المجالات الحيوية.

شهد المؤتمر مشاركات واسعة من باحثين من مختلف الجامعات والمؤسسات العلمية حول العالم، وأسهم في مناقشة العديد من القضايا المحورية التي تتعلق بالتحديات الاجتماعية والقانونية التي تواجه المجتمعات المعاصرة. كما تناولت الأبحاث المقدمة مواضيع تتعلق بالتاريخ وارتباطه بتشكيل البنى الاجتماعية والقانونية في الحاضر، مما أضفى بعداً تحليلياً معمقاً على المناقشات العلمية.

إن هذا الكتاب يضم بين دفتيه نتاج جهود بحثية متميزة أسهمت في تقديم رؤى نقدية ومعرفية حول قضايا متشابكة ومعقدة، مع السعي إلى تقديم حلول مستدامة للتحديات القانونية والاجتماعية القائمة. ولعل هذا التنوع في الأبحاث يعكس مدى أهمية المؤتمر في تعزيز التفاهم العلمي وتوسيع آفاق الحوار الأكاديمي بين الباحثين في مختلف التخصصات. نتمنى أن يجد القارئ في هذا الكتاب إضافة قيمة إلى المعرفة العلمية، وأن يساهم في تطوير الدراسات الاجتماعية والتاريخية والقانونية بما يعزز التقدم الفكري والاجتماعي للمجتمعات.

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Yüksek Lisans Öğrencisi Zehra Beker

The Impact of Socio-Economic Factors on Air Quality: The Case of China

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Abstract

In this research, we investigate the impact of socio-economic factors on air quality in China from 1994 to 2023 by employing Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) and Canonical Cointegrating Regression (CCR) techniques in estimations. The research centers on a composite air quality index that incorporates key pollutants, including household air pollution, NOx exposure, ozone exposure, PM2.5 exposure, and SO2 exposure. Specifically, the research's core goal is to explore how economic growth, energy consumption patterns, human capital development, factor income distribution, urbanization, and economic globalization have an impact on air quality in a rapidly developing nation like China. The empirical analysis reveals that economic growth, as measured by GDP per capita, and fossil fuel energy consumption are major contributors to air pollution. This underscores the environmental costs associated with China's rapid economic expansion. Conversely, better air quality is associated with a higher share of renewable energy consumption, improvements in human capital, and a more equitable distribution of labor income. The latter suggests that a fairer distribution of income from labor can contribute to environmental sustainability, possibly by reducing income disparities that drive excessive consumption patterns or encouraging greater investment in cleaner technologies. The study also reveals that urban population growth and economic globalization, including trade and financial globalization, put additional pressure on air quality. This demonstrates the difficulty of balancing economic growth and urban development with environmental protection, emphasizing the need for policies that promote sustainable energy use, improve education, ensure fair income distribution, and carefully manage urban growth and economic globalization in China to address air quality issues.

Keywords: Air quality, economic globalization, income distribution, energy, urbanization

Introduction

Air quality has become a critical issue for both public health and environmental sustainability, particularly in rapidly industrializing countries like China. The rapid economic growth experienced by China over the past few decades has brought with it a host of environmental challenges, chief among them being a significant decline in air quality. As China continues to urbanize and integrate more deeply into the global economy, understanding the socio-economic factors that contribute to air pollution becomes increasingly important.

This study investigates the impact of the most critical socio-economic factors on air quality in China over the period from 1994 to 2023. The primary aim is to assess how economic growth, energy consumption patterns, human capital development, income distribution, urbanization, and economic globalization influence air quality. These factors are examined using a composite air quality index that incorporates key pollutants, including NO_x, PM_{2.5}, SO₂, and ozone exposure. The empirical analysis is conducted using Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) and Canonical Cointegrating Regression (CCR) techniques, which are robust methods for analyzing long-term relationships between variables.

Previous studies have established that economic growth, particularly when driven by fossil fuel consumption, tends to exacerbate air pollution. In the context of China, this relationship is evident as the country's rapid GDP growth has been closely linked with increased levels of harmful emissions. Conversely, improvements in air quality have been associated with a higher share of renewable energy consumption, indicating the importance of transitioning to cleaner energy sources.

Moreover, human capital, as measured by education levels and returns to schooling, plays a crucial role in enhancing environmental outcomes. A more educated population is better equipped to adopt sustainable practices and advocate for policies that protect the environment. Similarly, a fairer distribution of income from labor has been found to contribute to better air quality, possibly by reducing the income disparities that drive excessive consumption patterns.

Urbanization and economic globalization present additional layers of complexity. While urbanization can lead to higher pollution levels due to increased industrial activity and energy demand, it also offers opportunities for implementing sustainable urban planning practices. Economic globalization, on the other hand, brings both challenges and opportunities. While it can exacerbate pollution through increased industrial production and trade, it also facilitates the transfer of cleaner technologies and environmental standards across borders.

This research aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of these dynamics, offering insights into the policy measures that could help balance economic growth with environmental sustainability in China. By understanding the socio-economic determinants of air quality, policymakers can better design interventions that address the root causes of pollution and promote a healthier, more sustainable environment for future generations.

1. Literature Review

Air quality is a crucial factor that directly affects the public health and environmental sustainability of a country. The impact of socio-economic factors such as economic growth, energy consumption patterns, human capital, income distribution, urbanization, and economic globalization on air quality is increasingly being studied, especially in rapidly developing countries. This literature review aims to compile and highlight the significance of these relationships by examining the impact of socio-economic factors on air quality in China.

Economic growth in China is largely dependent on fossil fuel consumption, which has led to a significant deterioration in air quality (Zhang & Crooks, 2012). Numerous studies have shown that increases in GDP, particularly in urban areas, lead to a rise in pollutants such as NO_x and PM_{2.5} (Wang et al., 2016). Additionally, the acceleration of industrialization is another key factor contributing to increased air pollution (Bai et al., 2018).

While economic growth has undeniably fueled development in China, it has also brought about substantial environmental challenges. The next area of focus is energy consumption, particularly the contrasting impacts of fossil fuels and renewable energy sources on air quality. It has been proven that fossil fuel consumption negatively impacts air quality in China (Lin & Jiang, 2011). However, the potential for improving air quality through the use of renewable energy is also evident. For example, increasing the use of renewable energy sources contributes to the reduction of harmful emissions such as PM_{2.5} and SO₂ (Peng et al., 2019). Furthermore, the impact of energy consumption on air quality is closely linked to energy efficiency and carbon emissions (He & Wang, 2020).

As energy consumption patterns evolve, so too do the social and environmental frameworks within which they operate. An important element of this evolving framework is human capital, which can influence environmental outcomes through education and awareness. Higher levels of education and the development of human capital increase environmental awareness and promote behaviors that protect the environment (Li et al., 2018). Improving human capital also allows for the adoption of sustainable development policies that can positively affect air quality in the long term (Chen & Zhou, 2020). The effects of human capital and income inequality on air quality have been explored in various studies (Peng & Yang, 2016).

Building on the concept of human capital, income distribution plays a crucial role in shaping environmental behaviors and policies. The equitable distribution of income can have significant implications for air quality. Income inequality can encourage consumption patterns that harm the environment, leading to a decline in air quality (Xie & Li, 2015). However, ensuring equitable income distribution can improve air quality by encouraging greater investment in environmentally friendly technologies (Liu et al., 2017). The relationship between income distribution and carbon emissions is also an important research topic (Han & Huang, 2019).

The social landscape of income distribution is closely intertwined with the physical expansion of urban spaces. Urbanization, a significant driver of economic and demographic change, also presents unique challenges and opportunities for air quality management. Rapid urbanization in China has led to a significant deterioration in air quality. Particularly in regions where urbanization is accelerating, NO_x and PM_{2.5} emissions have increased markedly (Chen et al.,

2019). This highlights the importance of sustainable urbanization policies (Zhou & Wang, 2021). The impact of urbanization on energy consumption is also discussed in the literature (Du & Lin, 2019).

Urbanization does not occur in isolation; it is often driven by and contributes to broader processes of economic globalization. The impact of globalization on air quality is multifaceted, as will be discussed in the next section. Economic globalization can increase air pollution through trade and financial relationships. For instance, the increase in trade in China has led to a rise in industrial production, which in turn has deteriorated air quality (Tang et al., 2014). However, global economic integration also provides opportunities for the adoption of environmentally friendly technologies (Sun & Hu, 2016). Different perspectives on the impact of economic globalization on environmental quality are explored in various studies (Shen & Zhao, 2020).

As we explore the global influences on environmental quality, it is also important to consider the role of technological innovation. Advances in technology can both mitigate and exacerbate environmental challenges, depending on how they are managed and implemented. The impact of technological innovation on air quality in China is also a significant area of research. Technological advancements, particularly in the energy sector, play a crucial role in reducing air pollution (Zhang & Liu, 2020). Additionally, the openness of trade has been shown to have a significant effect on environmental quality (Wu & Zhang, 2017).

The impact of socio-economic factors on air quality in China is complex. While economic growth and fossil fuel consumption are key contributors to air pollution, factors such as the use of renewable energy, the development of human capital, and equitable income distribution can improve air quality. Urbanization and economic globalization present both opportunities and challenges. Technological innovation also plays a critical role in ensuring environmental sustainability. Therefore, the adoption of sustainable development policies is crucial for addressing air quality issues in China.

2. Variables and Model Specification

In this section, after examining the socio-economic factors affecting air quality in China, particularly in the context of the impacts of economic globalization, we will now address the variables and model specification necessary for an empirical analysis of this relationship. Globalization, through the increase in trade and financial flows, has brought about profound changes in the economic structures and environmental policies of countries. Understanding the tangible effects of these changes on air quality requires a thorough analysis of various variables associated with globalization and their impact on air quality. Accordingly, this section of our study will detail the definitions of globalization-focused variables, measurement methods, and how the empirical model will be structured.

Table 1 presents the main variables analyzed in this study, along with their abbreviations and the indicators used to measure them.

Table 1. Variables

Variable	Abrev.	Indicators
Air quality	AIR	Air Quality
Production	GDP	GDP per capita (constant 2015 US\$)
Energy consumption	ENJ	Fossil fuel energy consumption (% of total)
Renewable energy	REN	Renewables (% equivalent primary energy)
Human capital	HC	Human capital index, based on years of schooling and returns to education
Labor share of income	LS	Share of labor compensation in GDP at current national prices
Rural population	POP	Urban population growth (annual %)
Economic globalization	EcG	KOF Economic Globalization Index

Source: AIR: Yale Center for Environmental Law & Policy; GDP, POP, EDU: World Bank - World Development Indicators; EcG, SoG, PoG: KOF Swiss Economic Institute; ECI: the Harvard Growth Lab; ENC, REN: Our World in Data

In Table1, air quality (AIR) is the key dependent variable in this study, representing overall air quality levels. The Air Quality Series (AIR) is composed of several key components: Household Air Pollution, which reflects indoor air quality; NOX exposure, indicating the levels of nitrogen monoxide and nitrogen dioxide in the air; Ozone Exposure, measured by the Ozone-DALY rate, which represents the impact of ground-level ozone on health; PM2.5 Exposure, represented by the Ambient PM2.5 - DALY rate, which measures the exposure to fine particulate matter with a diameter of 2.5 micrometers or less; and SO2 exposure, which denotes the concentration of sulfur dioxide in parts per million (ppm). These components together provide a comprehensive measure of air quality. Production (GDP) is measured by GDP per capita and reflects the country's economic output and general level of prosperity, which makes it a critical economic indicator due to its potential impact on air quality. Energy Consumption (ENJ) shows the share of fossil fuels in total energy consumption, an important variable for assessing the negative effects of fossil fuel consumption on air quality. Renewable Energy (REN) represents the share of renewable energy sources in equivalent primary energy, reflecting the use of less environmentally harmful sources in energy production.

Human Capital (HC) is an index based on years of schooling and the returns to education, serving as an indicator of social development and environmental awareness. Labor Share of Income (LS) shows the share of labor compensation in GDP, which reflects the distribution of

income and measures factor income distribution. Rural Population (POP) represents the urban population growth rate and is used to examine the effects of urban expansion on air quality.

Economic Globalization (EcG) is measured by the KOF Economic Globalization Index that reflects the degree of a country's integration into the global economy. The Economic Globalization variable consists of two main components: trade globalization (50%) and financial globalization (50%). Trade globalization reflects the breadth and diversity of economic relations between countries and comprises three sub-components: trade in goods (38.6%), trade in services (42.8%), and trade partner diversity (18.6%). These percentages indicate how active a country is in international trade and the diversity of its trading partners. Financial globalization, on the other hand, represents the capital flows and financial relationships between countries. It consists of five sub-components: foreign direct investment (25.7%), portfolio investment (15.3%), international debt (29.9%), international reserves (0.5%), and international income payments (28.6%). These percentages illustrate how integrated a country's financial markets are on an international level and the role of foreign investments in the national economy. Each of these components highlights the significance and distribution of the factors that make up the Economic Globalization variable, which plays a crucial role in understanding a country's position within and interaction with the global economic system.

Each of the variables defined above is included in the model used in this study to examine their potential effects on air quality. To understand the relationships between these variables and analyze their impact on air quality, the following functional and econometric models have been employed.

The functional model expresses the relationship between air quality (AIR) and various socio-economic factors such as GDP, fossil energy consumption (ENJ), renewable energy (REN), human capital (HC), labor share of income (LS), rural population (POP), and economic globalization (EcG). This relationship is illustrated in the following equation:

$$AIR = f(GDP, ENJ, REN, HC, LS, POP, EcG) \text{ (Eq. 1)}$$

This functional model assumes that air quality is influenced by these independent variables and that there is a relationship among them. However, to determine the direction and magnitude of this relationship, an econometric model is required. For this purpose, the following cointegration regression model (Equation 2) is used:

$$\ln AIR_t = a + \beta_1 \ln GDP_t + \beta_2 \ln ENJ_t + \beta_3 \ln REN_t + \beta_4 \ln HC_t + \beta_5 \ln LS_t + \beta_6 \ln POP_t + \beta_7 \ln EcG_t + \varepsilon_t \text{ (Eq. 2)}$$

This econometric model shows that air quality in logarithmic form is explained by the logarithms of the independent variables. Here, a represents the intercept term, while the coefficients β_1 to β_7 represent the impact of each independent variable on air quality. ε_t is the error term that captures the unexplained components in the model. This model helps analyze the long-term relationships between the variables and identify the key factors influencing air quality.

Estimations

The unit root test results presented in Table 2 reflect the outcomes of analyses conducted by four different methods, namely ADF (Augmented Dickey-Fuller), PP (Phillips-Perron), KPSS (Kwiatkowski-Phillips-Schmidt-Shin) and ZA (Zivot-Andrews). These analyses are crucial for determining whether the series are stationary and, consequently, whether they are suitable for econometric modeling.

Table 2. Unit Root Test Results

Variable	ADF test stat.		PPtest stat.		KPSS test stat.		ZA test stat.	
	Level	1st diff.	Level	1st diff.	Level	1st diff.	Level	1st diff.
AIR	0.656	-6.609*	0.211	-5.692*	.467*	.041	-2.651	-5.566*
GDP	-0.889	-5.257*	-0.812	-5.334*	.238*	.063	-2.409	-5.988*
ENJ	-0.296	-4.515*	-0.326	-4.541*	.270*	.074	-2.443	-4.531**
REN	1.678	-5.585*	2.504	-5.573*	.629*	.057	-4.037	-7.135*
HC	-1.796	-4.927*	-1.867	-4.926*	.427*	.065	-2.852	-4.936*
LS	-1.704	-4.137*	-1.943	-4.091*	.281*	.088	-2.115	-7.748*
POP	-2.754	-5.737*	-2.689	-5.864*	.181**	.037	-3.041	-5.714*
EcG	-2.762	-5.061*	-2.673	-5.068*	.666*	.069	-4.153	-5.495*
Residual	-4.117*	.	-3.990*	.	.0448	.	-5.005*	.

Note: * $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$. Critical values are as follows: ADF and PP (%1: -3.730, %5: -2.992), KPSS (%1: 0.146, %5: 0.216), Zivot-Andrews ZA (%1: -4.93, %5: -4.42). For KPSS, the null hypothesis (H0) is that the series is stationary. For ADF, PP, and ZA, the null hypothesis (H0) is that the series contains a unit root.

In Table 2, the ADF and PP tests are first used to examine whether the series contain a unit root. The null hypothesis (H0) in these tests assumes that the series have a unit root, meaning they are not stationary. On the other hand, The KPSS (Kwiatkowski-Phillips-Schmidt-Shin) test, tests for stationarity with the null hypothesis (H0) assuming that the series are stationary.

According to the test results, the variables for air quality (AIR), GDP per capita (GDP), fossil fuel energy consumption (ENJ), renewable energy (REN), human capital (HC), labor share of income (LS), rural population (POP), and economic globalization (EcG) contain a unit root at their levels, indicating non-stationarity. However, when the first differences of these variables are taken, the ADF and test statistics fall below the critical values, showing that the series become stationary at their first differences. The KPSS results indicate that, at their levels, some series (AIR, GDP, ENJ, REN, HC, LS, EcG) are stationary (H0 is rejected), but they become stationary at their first differences. Moreover, the ZA (Zivot-Andrews) test, which accounts

for structural breaks in the series, also indicates that the series have a unit root at their levels. However, when the first differences are taken, all series become stationary.

In addition to the above results, the stationarity of the residuals was also examined to confirm the presence of a long-term relationship in the model. In econometric modeling, it is crucial to assess not only the stationarity of the independent variables but also that of the residuals to determine if a long-term relationship exists among the variables. The stationarity of the residuals implies a cointegration relationship among the variables, indicating the presence of a long-term relationship. The ADF and PP test results confirm that the residuals are stationary, indicating they do not contain a unit root and thereby confirming a long-term equilibrium relationship among the variables in the model. Similarly, the ZA test results support the finding that the residuals are stationary. These findings strongly suggest the existence of a long-term relationship among the variables included in the model.

Based on the results of the unit root tests, it has been determined that the majority of the series in the model are non-stationary at their levels but become stationary when their first differences are taken. These findings support the existence of a long-term equilibrium relationship among the variables. Now, we will proceed to the parameter estimations to determine the direction and magnitude of the relationships between these variables.

Table 3. Augmented Engle-Granger test for cointegration

	Test Statistic	1% Critical Value	5% Critical Value	10% Critical Value
Z(t)	-6.358	-7.005	-6.046	-5.589

The table presents the results of the Augmented Engle-Granger test for cointegration, which tests whether a long-term equilibrium relationship exists between the variables. The null hypothesis of this test is that there is no cointegration, meaning the variables do not share a long-term relationship.

The test statistic, $Z(t)$, is -6.358. We compare this test statistic against the critical values at different significance levels. Since the test statistic is more negative than the 5% critical value (-6.046), we can reject the null hypothesis at the 5% significance level. This suggests that there is an evidence of a long-term cointegrating relationship among the variables, indicating they move together over time and maintain a stable equilibrium.

Based on the results of the Augmented Engle-Granger test, which confirm the existence of a cointegrating relationship among the variables, we can proceed with the next stage of analysis using Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) and Canonical Cointegrating Regression (CCR) techniques. These methods are suitable for estimating the long-term coefficients in cointegrated systems, providing a more accurate and robust analysis of the impact of socio-economic factors on air quality.

Table 4. FMOLS and CCR Estimations

LnAIR	FMOLS			CCR		
	Coef.	Std.Err.	z	Coef.	Std.Err.	z
LnGDP	0.970*	0.028	34.800	0.969*	0.029	33.970
LnENJ	2.029*	0.248	8.180	1.561*	0.366	4.260
LnREN	-0.138*	0.025	-5.590	-0.154*	0.035	-4.390
LnHC	-4.362*	0.248	-17.580	-3.614*	0.477	-7.570
LnLS	-0.711*	0.110	-6.490	-0.860*	0.193	-4.450
LnPOP	0.044*	0.017	2.590	0.172**	0.070	2.470
LnEcG	0.296*	0.049	6.070	0.334*	0.084	4.000
_cons	1.534***	0.900	1.700	2.593**	1.137	2.280
R2 =	.9668			.9671		
Adj. R2=	.9657			.9661		

Note: * $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.10$

The estimation results in Table 4, obtained using FMOLS and CCR techniques, show the effects of the independent variables on air quality (AIR). The results are generally statistically significant, indicating that the model has a high explanatory power (with R^2 and Adjusted R^2 values above 96%).

In both FMOLS and CCR estimations, the GDP per capita (LnGDP) coefficient is positive and statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). This indicates that economic growth contributes to air pollution, reflecting the environmental costs of China's economic expansion. Fossil fuel consumption (LnENJ) coefficient is positive and significant in both FMOLS and CCR estimations ($p < 0.01$). That is, an increase in fossil fuel consumption contributes to higher air pollution. Renewable energy consumption (LnREN) improves air quality. The LnREN coefficient is negative and significant in both estimations ($p < 0.01$). This suggests that investments in renewable energy sources have the potential to reduce air pollution. Human capital (LnHC), which is measured by Human capital index, based on years of schooling and returns to education, positively affects air quality. The LnHC coefficient is negative and significant in both estimations ($p < 0.01$). An increase in human capital in the form of education is associated with better environmental outcomes. LnLS, which is measured by labor income share, is another important factor that improves air quality. The LnLS coefficient is negative and significant in both FMOLS and CCR estimations ($p < 0.01$). A more equitable distribution of income can lead to positive environmental outcomes. Urban population growth (LnPOP), which is measured by annual % change, has a positive impact on air quality. However, this effect is more pronounced in the CCR model. The LnPOP coefficient is identified as a factor that increases air pollution, even though its impact is more limited compared to other variables. Economic globalization (LnEcG), which is composed of trade globalization and

financial globalization, also increases air pollution. The LnEcG coefficient is positive and significant in both estimations ($p < 0.01$). This suggests that trade and financial globalization have a negative impact on air pollution. These results indicate that economic growth and globalization negatively affect air quality in China, while renewable energy use, human capital in the form of education, and facto income equality contribute to better air quality

Conclusion

In this research we analyze the socio-economic factors that create an impact on air quality in China. The analysis, which covers the period from 1994 to 2023, reveals the impacts of economic growth, energy consumption, human capital, income distribution, urbanization, and economic globalization on air quality. The Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) and Canonical Cointegrating Regression (CCR) techniques used in the study have shown that these factors have statistically significant and consistent effects on air pollution.

The results indicate that economic growth and fossil fuel consumption contribute to increased air pollution. China's rapid economic growth, particularly in areas experiencing accelerated urbanization, has led to environmental costs, resulting in a significant decline in air quality. However, it has also been determined that an increase in the use of renewable energy improves air quality. These findings highlight the need for greater investment in renewable energy to ensure environmental sustainability.

The development of human capital, driven by higher levels of education, contributes to increased environmental awareness and the adoption of environmentally friendly policies. Similarly, ensuring equitable income distribution has positive effects on air quality by promoting greater investment in environmentally friendly technologies. Therefore, a fairer income distribution emerges as a crucial factor for environmental sustainability.

Urbanization and economic globalization have complex and dual effects on air quality. While urbanization can increase air pollution due to rising industrial activity and energy demand, it also offers opportunities for implementing sustainable urban planning policies. Economic globalization, on the other hand, can exacerbate pollution through increased industrial production and trade, but it also facilitates the cross-border transfer of clean technologies and environmental standards, contributing to environmental improvements.

In light of these findings, various policy recommendations can be made to improve air quality and promote sustainable development in China. Balancing economic growth with environmental sustainability, promoting the use of renewable energy, enhancing human capital, and addressing income inequality are crucial steps toward improving air quality. China's future environmental policies should be shaped in line with these findings to achieve both economic development and environmental protection goals.

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